

Policy & Process – Software Lessons Learned in the DoD

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Introduction

❖ Matt Palmer

- Chief Engineer for the Joint Staff Command & Control Portfolio in the Department of Defense.
- Global Command & Control System (GCCS) – Most widely used piece of software in DoD

Topics

- ❖ What Makes a Software Project Successful vs Unsuccessful?
- ❖ The Operational Value of MVPs & Iterative Development.
- ❖ Why DoD Budget & Contract processes are terrible for Software.
- ❖ Agile – Does it work in large Government bureaucracies? (yes...but)
- ❖ DevSecOps – Does it work in large Government bureaucracies? (yes...but)
- ❖ Artificial Intelligence – what has & hasn't worked well in DoD
- ❖ Open-Source Software in Sensitive DoD Missions? (yes...no buts!)
- ❖ Q&A

What Makes a Software Project Successful vs Unsuccessful?

❖ In a Word - SCOPE

- Product Team Control of Scope.
- Functional, Technical, and Marketing perspectives.

❖ In Practice – Define and control your MVP (Minimum Viable Product).

- All Milestones leading up to your MVP must be well understood and definable by your product team
- $A + B + C = \text{MVP 1.0}$
- Milestones must be deconstructed into some sub-milestones and dependencies.
- Sub Milestones continue to break down into smaller, manageable piece. Ex: Milestone A -> A.1 -> A.1.1 -> A1.1.1 ... A1.1.1.x where x = the level of granularity by which your team can accurately estimate cost, time, & responsibility/ownership.
- If you have an MVP which breaks the above rules it is probably not a good MVP candidate

Operational Value of MVP's & Iterative Development

❖ MVP's must deliver operational value???

- Not necessarily. It must be a valid steppingstone to operational value.
- Significant Executive/Political pressure to deliver operational value in MVP = scope explosion.
- Venture Capital in Private Industry – ex: UBER
- In Government, treat MVP's like Toddlers...

❖ MVP vs. MVC

- MVC = Minimum Viable Capability (first operationally valuable solution negotiated w/ community)
- MVC = MVP 1.x (where x is almost always > 0)
- Used when the product team & community cannot define an MVC or operational value right away.
- Requires lessons learned from MVP 1.x iterations
- Operational settings where user community has problems & goals, not requirements.
- Successive MVP iterations should provide better realism over your unknowns.

Why DoD Budget & contract processes are terrible for Software Systems.

- ❖ DoD treats software like traditional equipment. DoD want contracts with:
 - A fixed set of definable, testable requirements & a fixed set of costs.
 - All this to be known up front at project initiation.
 - Software is not like a Car.
 - Historic models of Software costs rarely good indicators of future projects.
 - Once a car design is built and operationalized, it rarely changes. Software is organic.
- ❖ DoD Budgets
 - Segregation of R&D and Operational Funding – not applicable to Software!
 - Uses Yearly appropriations for Software which complicate over multiple fiscal years and CR's.
 - If your requirements are unknowns – contract for KSA's and teaming arrangements]
 - Avoid 'Monster' software contracts if you can.
 - Use pilots, prototypes, and OTA's for year 1-2, then follow up years 3-5 with 'Monster' contract

Agile – Does it work in large Government Bureaucracies?

❖ Agile in DoD

- It works under the right circumstances
- Your Software Dev Team being Agile != Your project being Agile
- DoD is not structured for Agility, it's structured for checks & balances (decentralization of power)
- Separate agencies and authorities across software project lifecycle
- Bureaucracy = a decentralization of power/control. Success through consensus.

❖ To Make Agile Effective you must have Collaboration

- Product Teams over Software Teams
- May mean significant increases in Government Staff
- Works well in R&D, Low Cost settings, and where Agile Executives have centralized control
- Become an Agile 'Lobbyist' within the cyber, test, policy, and oversight areas of your organization
- Not always about a 'resistance to change' culture.

Artificial Intelligence – what has and hasn't worked in DoD

❖ Can be helpful to start off with where it hasn't work well:

- 1 - Missions with bad data, confused data ownership etc...
- 2 - Missions with significant Regulatory Standards.
- Example: NBIS (National Background Investigation Service)
- AI not good with 'corner cases' or 'boundary cases'
- AI not good with confusing policy cases.
- Not good with data on humans (historic data biases or requires legal traceability)

❖ Where AI has worked well at DoD

- PANDA – Predictive Analytics and Decision Assistant
- Airforce human-machine pairing application to assist with aircraft maintenance & component part replacement prioritization
- Geared towards a function humans are not good at
- Non-controversial regarding human data

Open-Source Software in Sensitive DoD Missions (yes...no buts!)

- ❖ Finally, a topic that can just be answered with a Yes!
 - Proprietary, protected corporate software utilizes open source software, standards, and libraries anyway – not getting away from it!
 - Log4j – most well known open source library vulnerability in DoD
 - Better to have a full tabulation of the open source software up front than have it ‘hidden’ in a corporate proprietary tech stack.
 - Mitigate risk by not relying on build dependencies within environments that have commercial connectivity.
 - Functionally, it’s best to keep proprietary software as far up the tech stack as possible, away from your core data (core data should utilize open standards, no corporate data model etc...)

Questions?

❖ Questions and Comments!